

Highlights

Reusability analysis metrics for 2nd life electrical and mechanical battery components

Dimitra Spanoudaki, Vasileios Apostoloudas, Elisavet Elvanoglou

- Second-Life batteries
- Mechanical waste
- Electrical waste
- Reusability analysis
- Circularity

Preprint not peer reviewed

Reusability analysis metrics for 2nd life electrical and mechanical battery components*

Dimitra Spanoudaki^{a,*}, Vasileios Apostoloudas^{a,1} and Elisavet Elvanoglou^a

^aSunlight Group Energy Systems, Lithium - Research and Development Department, , Xanthi, 67200, Greece

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

2nd life batteries
reusability analysis
waste management
lithium-ion batteries

ABSTRACT

In the near future, the number of electric vehicle (EV) batteries, no longer appropriate for automotive use, will dramatically increase. At the end of their warranties the expected EV batteries nominal capacity will vary between 70–80%. This is also the First-Life End-Of-Life threshold adopted by most within the automotive industry. Whereas these EV batteries will not be appropriate for automotive applications, they could be repurposed for stationary energy storage systems as Second-Life batteries. The new Battery Regulation of the European Union is enforced as of July 2023 and ensures that batteries within the EU have a low carbon footprint due to the reduction of resources required, the reduction of raw materials (from non-EU countries) and an increase of reuse and recycling in Europe. The result of this act is the shift to a circular economy growth model, the increase in security of supply for raw materials and energy overall and the enhancement of the EU's strategic autonomy. Working towards the direction of the circular economy growth model, we present the first steps a battery industry must take for the repurposing of 1st life traction batteries (industrial EV's) for an industrial stationary energy storage system. More specifically, we address the issue of the reusability of first life electrical and mechanical components (except for the lithium-ion cells), and we introduce quantitative and decision-making tools for an automatic and safer choice of these components for the Second-Life applications. The methodology of the reusability analysis of a Second-Life battery, includes the evaluation of the Bill of Materials (BOM) list of the battery system, the grouping and sorting of the different materials, their evaluation from engineers and blue-collar workers and the final assessment with a decision matrix. The criteria introduced in the decision matrix include the price, the volume, the warranty, the environmental impact, the availability (in the market) and the recyclability of the electrical and mechanical components. The results of this assessment show a trend on how many of the electrical and mechanical components are suggested to be recycled or repurposed for Second-Life applications based on each one of the main criteria we introduced in the decision matrix.

Acronym	Meaning
EV	Electric Vehicle
BS	Battery System
BOM	Bill of Materials
NMC	Nickel manganese Cobalt cells
LFP	Lithium Iron Phosphate
BESS	Battery Energy Storage System

Table 1

Abbreviations related to battery systems and circular economy notions.

1. Introduction

Since the Industrial Revolution, the dominating economic growth model is a linear model that serves the purposes of a rapid and efficient production of goods, without regard to environmental resources. In the last few decades,

* Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor CINEA can be held responsible for these issues. Grant Agreement number: 101137615

*Corresponding author

 d.spanoudaki@sunlight.gr (D. Spanoudaki)

ORCID(s): 0000-0001-7511-2910 (D. Spanoudaki)

¹These authors contributed equally to this manuscript.

manufacturing firms have been facing great challenges including resource scarcity, soaring prices of energy and materials, environmental pollutions and societal pressures. These challenges have forced governments to regulate in favor of a new circular economy growth model and firms to find ways to adopt circular methodologies and thinking of production procedures Lacy, Long and Spindler (2020); OECD (2019).

A circular economy is a regenerative economic model in which resource input emissions, waste and energy leakage are minimized by slowing, narrowing and closing the material and energy loops Foundation (2015). A circular economy aims to keep resources in productive use for as possible, extract the maximum value from them whilst in use, then recover and regenerate products and/or raw materials at the end of their service life. By closing the loop of material flows throughout the product life cycle and using the raw material and energy through multiple phases, the circular approach seeks to ultimately decouple economic growth from constrained natural resources.

A robust example of an international try for efficient circular management is that of the Li-ion batteries. The exponential increase in the adoption of electric vehicles (EVs) poses a pressing concern about the end-of-life management of the Li-ion batteries. By 2030, it is expected that more than 145 million EVs will be in the society. Li-ion batteries have a lifespan ranging from 5 - 15 years and their capacity reduction drops as much as 20%. Due to their

Figure 1: Reusability analysis methodology for the evaluation of the components of a 1st life battery system.

decreased performance in EVs and due to concerns about their safety, new applications have been investigated for these batteries in the field of Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS), giving them a second life in another less demanding applications Sathre, Scown, Kavvada and Hendrickson (2015); Chirumalla, Kulkov, Vu and Rahic (2023); Dong, Liang, Li, Kim, Shen and Wallington (2023); Cusenza, Guarino, Longo, Ferraro and Cellura (2019); Neigum and Wang (2024); Wu, Lin, Xie, Elliott and Radcliffe (2020).

Despite the growing body of literature on reuse and repurposing of EV batteries, a discernible gap persists in the examination of the repurposing of the waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) that they co-exist with the to-be-repurposed battery cells inside a battery pack.

In this research, we aim to address the issue of the reusability of WEEE and to introduce quantitative and decision-making tools for an automatic and rational choice of WEEE to be reused. We consider the by-default repurposing of battery modules, for a second life BESS and we evaluate the reusability of WEEE Sun, Dong, Dai, Dong, Fujii, Geng, Lou and Liu (2024)

This manuscript consists of: 1) the introduction of the decision-making methodology, 2) the application of the methodology to traction batteries and 3) the discussion of the results.

2. Methodology

To evaluate the re-usability of the components of the 1st life battery system and the possibility of re-purposing it to a 2nd life BESS, we developed a methodology that includes the

assessment of the components through the Bill of Materials (BOM) of the 1st life battery system. Figure 1 presents the methodology and the basic steps identified are the following:

- The BOM list (Table 1) is the main tool to proceed in the reusability analysis. The BOM list is the main list that includes every mechanical, electronic or other (sticker, glues) component that is used to build a battery system (Fig. 2). It consists of various levels, from the higher systems to the lower subsystems. As we move from the higher to the lower level, we move from the outer part of the battery to the inner part and from the bigger parts to smaller ones. As a first step, we extract the important BOM levels for this assessment. For the 2nd life BESS, the modules of the 1st life battery system are going to be reused, so we will take into consideration the higher levels. In the example of the Table 2, we are going to evaluate the components of the levels 1, 2, and 3 because they are higher systems to the module (level 4), and we are not going to evaluate the re-usability of the levels 5 and 6, because they exist in the module that is going to be re-used.
- The 2nd step is the 01 Assessment (Fig. 1). This assessment is done by 3 reviewers – an electrical engineer, a mechanical engineer and a blue-collar worker – who decide if a battery component is going to be disposed or reused based on their experience and their knowledge. If they choose its disposal, they grade the battery component with 0 and if they choose its reuse,

Level	Component Description	Quantity	Units
1	battery display	1	pieces
1	CAN BUS cable	7	meters
1	plastic head bolt	10	pieces
1	rubber sheet vibration	1	
1	cable tie	30	pieces
2	NMC modules 85 kWh	16	pieces
2	contactor SGX 150 A	4	pieces
2	fuse GigaFuse 100 V - 400 A	1	pieces
2	cable tie	80	pieces
2	silicone tube	6	meters
2	washers M4 INOX A2	24	pieces
2	NMC module	4	pieces
3	slave board	4	pieces
3	master board	1	pieces
3	screws	126	pieces
3	thermistors	2	pieces
3	washers M4 INOX A2	68	pieces
4	Pre-assembled module NMC	1	pieces
4	NMC cell	76	pieces
4	bolt M6x12 HEX DIN 933 INOX A4	224	pieces
4	Sticker "Minus - "	4	pieces
5	cable UL	6	meters
5	silicone tube	7	meters
5	thermistor	32	pieces
5	Minifit female connector	6	pieces
6	glue	100	milli-liters
6	thermal pipe	1	meters
6	wire yellow	1	meters
6	wire blue	1	meters

Table 2
An example of a Bill of Materials list of a battery system.

they grade the battery component with 1. In case of doubts, our recommendation to the reviewers is to choose 1. After their evaluation, the decision is made from the final score produced by summarizing the 0's and 1's. Scoring above 2 means that a component can be reused and below that, it needs to be disposed, having no further usage for 2nd life battery system or any other kind of re-purposing process. If 2 of the 3 reviewers have chosen that a component A is going to be disposed (0) then their opinion prevails against the one reviewer. The goal for the 01 Assessment is an initial evaluation of reuse of the module components on quantitative level.

- The 3rd step is the re-evaluation of the positive 01 Assessment results based on well-defined decision criteria inserted on a Pugh decision matrix Burge (2006). If there is a value in the battery components that can be generated for a 2nd life application, the decision criteria will show it clearly.

In the next sections, a rigorous analysis of the steps is given.

Figure 2: Some of the components of a battery system Bill of Materials.

Groups	Parts	Material
1	washers	metal
2	screws	metal
3	bolts	metal
4	cables	plastic, metal
5	silicone, plastic, heat tubing	plastic
6	nuts	metal
7	harness	plastic, metal
8	bus bars	metal

Table 3

Grouping of the various components of a battery system under a common name.

3. Methodology

3.1. Bill of Materials and 01 Assessment

A BOM list is a file that consists of the battery levels, the component description, their quantities and their units (Table 2). The levels refer to the level of the BS, meaning that the smaller numbers, i.e. 1, refer to the higher and outer level of the BS and as we move towards the smaller numbers, we move to the inner parts of a BS and to smaller components.

The component description is created by the designer of the 1st life BS based on a standard trend that developed and adopted by the industries. It contains information about the sizes of mechanical parts (i.e. Washers M4 INOX A2), current and voltage limits of electrical parts (i.e. Contactor SGX 150A, colors of wires (i.e. Wire yellow) etc. In the methodology, we grouped various components into eight categories (Table 3) based on their functionality, that is: 1) washers, 2) screws, 3) bolts, 4) cables, 5) silicone, plastic, heat tubing, 6) nus, 7) harness, 8) bus bars, so as to simplify their evaluation and not taking into account their sizes, colors or other characteristics that are irrelevant to the reusability decisions. Also, we indicate the material they are made of, that is metal, plastic or both of them.

3.2. Decision Matrix

Fundamentally a Pugh matrix can be used whenever there is a need to decide amongst several alternatives. Although specifically developed by Stuart Pugh to help in selecting between a few design alternatives, the tools have in recent years be used in general-purpose decision-making aid because its ease of use. The sole purpose of a Pugh decision matrix is to handle the inconsistent and irrational decisions of human beings. Because, the 01 Assessment of this research is highly based on personal choices of the evaluators, we need a more robust way to avoid biased decisions that we will present a distorted image of which component is being repurposed and which one is going to be recycled. For that requirement of objectiveness to be achieved, general criteria are selected, to research their impact on the remaining components after the 01 Assessment. These criteria are defined on Table 4 and in the list below:

- **Price:** This criterion represents the value of the component in the market. Higher prices mean components

with higher values and thus their repurposing process should be considered very wisely before any decision for recycling them.

- **Volume:** Volume of a component is highly considered during product development, due to product's final size and waste management. Waste management is an everyday issue for industries and gets of higher importance when its volume rises. To resolve this, in the spectrum of 2nd life BESS, components with large volume need to be reconsidered for reuse/repurpose than recycling, and this criterion showcases that. If a component has a volume above a specific range is accepted for reuse/repurpose, and below that range goes for recycling. This criterion is intended to set a limit to the quantitative evaluation, because many components to be reused, may have low volume (cables, screws, nuts, bolts).
- **Warranty:** The warranty of a component is an extremely important criterion because it is strongly linked to the safety of the product. A component, that its warranty has expired, will be treated differently than any other component, as the quality control will be more extensive and stricter. In general, the state of warranty of a BS is one of the most important reusability indicators because it has an indirect reference to the safety of the BS components.
- **Environmental Impact:** Some of the battery components have higher environmental impact if they are disposed accidentally or not to the environment and if they are sent to recycling. For example, bolts and nuts are consisting only of metal and their environmental impact its low, because they degrade by atmospheric oxidation if they are disposed in the environment. A wire that consists of metal and plastic it has higher environmental impact because the plastics do not decompose naturally in the environment, but they degrade to microplastics, that affect extremely the ecosystem in the long-term period (Sutkar, Gade-war and Dhulap (2023)). At last, a component with high environmental impact, i.e. electrochemical cell (battery cell), except of metal and plastic has toxic chemicals that in case of their leakage, affect the environment in the short term.
- **Availability:** The criterion of the availability of components is linked with their availability in the market and possible distortion of the availability due to geopolitical changes, supply chain disruptions, biological dangers. For example, during the COVID-19 pandemic, the semiconductor industry was severely hit, thus disrupting the industry of PCBs, a vital component for the batteries, and every electronic device nowadays. The availability of a component in the market and the constant tracking of this criterion can help the businesses earn a significant strategic advantage

Criteria Definition	Price	Volume	Warranty	Environm. impact	Availability	Recyclability
Reuse +	100 € / unit	100 cm ³	10 years	High	Low	Low
Repurpose B	10 - 100 € / unit	10 – 100 cm ³	1 – 10 years	Medium	Medium	Medium
Recycle -	10 € / unit	10 cm ³	1 year or no warranty	Low	High	High

Table 4
Decision criteria definitions based on the Reuse, Repurpose, and Recycle goals.

	Component A	Component B	Component C	Component D
Criterion 1	B	-	+	B
Criterion 2	B	-	+	B
Criterion 3	B	+	+	-
Criterion 4	B	-	+	-
Criterion 5	B	B	+	-
Criterion 6	B	B	B	+
Criterion 7	B	+	B	B
Criterion 8	B	-	-	-
Criterion 9	B	+	-	B
Criterion 10	B	+	+	-
Total +	0	4	6	1
Total -	0	-4	-2	-5
Total score	0	0	4	-4

Table 5
Example of a Pugh decision matrix.

and estimate if there is a need to reuse a component and regulate disruptions in the supply chain.

- **Recyclability:** Strongly linked to the criterion of the environmental impact of the components, as a component that has a lower environmental impact, has a higher recyclability. For example, a metal that has a lower environmental impact it's easy to recycle by melting it. By increasing the complexity and the chemical basis of the components, the recyclability complexity increases as well. This criterion also includes the cost of recycling as well. Considering that, in our example of a metal, it still has a higher recyclability because it will cost less to recycle it.

Table 5 shows a completed Pugh Matrix for four hypothetical components called A, B, C and D, which can be found along the top of the matrix. The components were evaluated against 10 hypothetical criteria. In constructing a Pugh matrix, on component, in this example "Component A" is selected as the "baseline". The baseline scores as "B" against all the criteria. The other components are then compared in a pairwise fashion against component A for each of the criteria. If a component is:

- Better than the baseline, a "+" is entered in the appropriate cell.
- Worse than the baseline, a "-" is entered in the appropriate cell.
- The same as the baseline, a "B" is entered in the appropriate cell.

For the hypothetical components and criteria of the Table 5:

- Component A is the baseline for all criteria.
- Component B is worse than component A in the criteria 1, 2, 4, 8.
- Component C is worse than component A in the criteria 8, 9.
- Component D is worse than component A in the criteria 3, 4, 5, 8 and 10.

The overall decision is presented in the total score, where "B" = 0, "+" = +1 and "-" = -1, and:

- If the score is 0, then the component is in the baseline and goes for re-purposing/ reusing.
- If the score is positive, then the component will be reused or repurposed.
- If the score is negative, the component will be recycled.

In this research, we do not aim to distinguish between the notions re-purposing and re-using, but we consider that the value of the component is regenerated and is going to be used again in a 2nd life application.

4. Results and Discussion

Three reviewers, an electrical engineer, a mechanical engineer and a blue-collar worker, filled the 01 Assessment

	Contactor	Bolts	Module 1P16S	Battery Control Unit	Battery Socket	Flat Cable	Washer
Price	B	-	+	+	-	-	-
Volume	B	+	+	+	-	-	+
Environmental Impact	B	-	+	+	-	B	-
Availability	B	-	+	+	B	B	-
Recyclability	B	-	+	B	B	B	-
Total Score	0	-4	5	4	-3	-2	-4
Result	Pass	Fail	Pass	Pass	Fail	Fail	Fail

Table 6
Pugh Decision matrix examples from the BS.

Figure 3: 01 Assessment for the traction battery.

matrix and chose if the components of a first life battery system (a traction battery) can be reused or disposed

With the Pugh decision matrix and the 6 criteria – price, volume, warranty, environmental impact, availability, recyclability – we further assess the results from the 01 Assessment (4). The 38.5 % of the battery components can be re-purposed in a 2nd life BS or reused in a 1st life BS, and the 61.5 % can be recycled.

Further analysis of the 38.5 % of the reused components shows that the 25.6 % are electrical components, the 7.7 % are mechanical components and the 5.1 % are other components (mostly plastics).

The low percentage of the mechanical components is due to the nuts, bolts, washers and other mechanical components that must be inspected for corrosion signs or other defects before being reused in another application. Other mechanical components might also need to be redesigned to fit the 2nd life BS. This is dependent from the application, its complexity and the components that need to be added during manufacturing.

Figure 4: Reusability analysis results after the Pugh Analysis Assessment

Table 6 shows the results of some important battery components. The main conclusions from the Table 6 are the following:

- **Bolts:** Score -4. Passed from the one criterion; decreased in total for 2nd life BS.
- **Module 1P16S:** Score 6. Passed from all the criteria for 2nd life BS.
- **Battery Control Unit:** Score 4. Passed from all the criteria for 2nd life BS.
- **Battery Socket:** Score -3. Passed from half of the criteria but declined for 2nd life.
- **Flat cable:** Score -2. Passed from four criteria but neglected for the remaining two and got declined for 2nd life.
- **Washer:** Score -4. Passed only from one criterion, neglected from the rest and declined for 2nd life.

The above examples show that a component can be neglected for 2nd life purposes, while being accepted at least by one criterion. A question that arises from this observation is the following: “Which components, accepted for 2nd life purposes, passed the criterion X?”

In Figure 5, two bars are shown for each criterion. The first bar indicates the percentage of the components that

Figure 5: A) Reuse/ Repurpose results of the Pugh analysis matrix, i) one-by-one criterion, ii) compared to total results..

accepted a positive sign (+) in the Pugh analysis matrix and the second bar of each criterion shows the normalized percentage from the total BOM list results. The last bar (BOM results) includes the percentage of accepted components from the Pugh analysis. For the criteria Volume, Warranty, Environmental impact and Recyclability, we observe that the decrease is high, which means that many components got neglected for 2nd life, while initially passed those criteria (one-by-one).

Figure 5 shows at least that a lot of components get declined from finding application on 2nd life BS. To better understand the connection of each criterion on the result, by normalizing the percentage values of reuse/ repurpose is normalized (Figure 6a) and two trending lines occur:

1. The Price and the Availability criteria, having initially (by one-by-one evaluation) 100 % regarding the Reuse/Repurpose result, affect the most the Pugh analysis. Between these two, Price criterion has more impact on the result, while having the minimum percentage decrease.
2. The Volume criterion is either the most neutral or the most controlling factor in the Pugh analysis. By neutral, it means that it does not having much impact on the result, which is due to the many components that passed this criterion. In addition, every component that got accepted from the Pugh analysis, seems to have passed the Volume criterion. This means that a component possibly needs to have this criterion passed to be accepted for Reuse/Repurpose. As initially planned, adding this criterion was a try to control the quantitative parameter.

Figure 6b shows the normalized results with the total studied BOM list , where the percentages for the components to be Reused/Repurposed or Recycled are 6 % less than the Pugh analysis ones. Figure 6c presents the Reuse/Repurpose and Recycle quantitative results for all the reusability analysis for 2nd life BS, in a nested pie chart format. In the center, the 01 Assessment results are shown. On the next level, the Pugh analysis results are shown, combined with the total studied BOM list (having again the Disposal percentage).

On the third and last level, the breakdown of the previous percentages, by component type (Mechanical, Electrical, Other) is shown. After the assessment of the Pugh analysis, the results show that the 32.6 % are going to be reused for 2nd life BS, the 52.2 % of the components are going to be recycled and the remaining 15.2 % will be disposed of. In summary, regarding components to be reused and repurposed, mechanical components show a huge loss, where the majority is selected to be recycled, as they are customized components designed only for 1st life BS. The quantities of electrical components are the most of the components that are to be reused, and the same amount is also forwarded to be recycled. To manage the high recycling result (52.2 %) on the next level of analysis, during disassembly, a thorough quality control is required for these components.

5. Conclusions and Perspectives

The key criteria that influence the reusability of the WEEE components of a traction battery are the price and the availability. With Price having a slightly higher impact. Volume acts as a prerequisite criterion for component acceptance. The 32.6 % of components are viable for Reuse/Repurpose, mostly electrical components. The 52.2 % are directed to Recycling, primarily Mechanical components due to their first-life-specific designs. The 15.2 % are marked for disposal. The current analysis suggests a need for targeted disassembly procedures, especially for components marked for Recycling. Implementing stringent quality checks can enhance the yield of reusable or repurposable components.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Dimitra Spanoudaki: Conceptualization of this study, Methodology, Writing - Original draft preparation, Review - editing, Investigation, Supervision, Project Administration.
Vasileios Apostoloudas: Conceptualization of this study, Methodology, Writing - Original draft preparation, Review - editing, Investigation, Visualization.
Elisavet Elvanoglou: Data curation, Review.

References

- Burge, S., 2006. The Systems Engineering Tool Box. Burge Hughes Walsh. URL: <https://www.burgehugheswalsh.co.uk/Uploaded/1/Documents/FMA-Tool-v1-1.pdf>.
- Chirumalla, K., Kulkov, I., Vu, F., Rahic, M., 2023. Second life use of li-ion batteries in the heavy-duty vehicle industry: Feasibilities of remanufacturing, repurposing, and reusing approaches. *Sustainable Production and Consumption* 42, 351–366. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2023.10.007>, doi:10.1016/j.spc.2023.10.007.
- Cusenza, M.A., Guarino, F., Longo, S., Ferraro, M., Cellura, M., 2019. Energy and environmental benefits of circular economy strategies: The case study of reusing used batteries from electric vehicles. *Journal of Energy Storage* 25, 100845. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2019.100845>, doi:10.1016/j.est.2019.100845.
- Dong, Q., Liang, S., Li, J., Kim, H.C., Shen, W., Wallington, T.J., 2023. Cost, energy, and carbon footprint benefits of second-life electric vehicle battery use. *iScience* 26, 107195. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2023.107195>, doi:10.1016/j.isci.2023.107195.

Figure 6: a. Pugh analysis normalized results, b. Pugh matrix results correlated on total quantities from the BOM list, c) Reusability analysis results for the 2nd life BS.

Foundation, E.M., 2015. Growth within: A circular economy vision for a competitive Europe. Ellen MacArthur Foundation. URL: <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/growth-within-a-circular-economy-vision-for-a-competitive-europe>.

Lacy, P., Long, J., Spindler, W., 2020. The Circular Economy Handbook: Realizing the Circular Advantage. Palgrave Macmillan UK. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1057/978-1-349-95968-6>, doi:10.1057/978-1-349-95968-6.

Neigum, K., Wang, Z., 2024. Technology, economic, and environmental analysis of second-life batteries as stationary energy storage: A review. Journal of Energy Storage 103, 114393. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2024.114393>, doi:10.1016/j.est.2024.114393.

OECD, 2019. Global Material Resources Outlook to 2060: Economic Drivers and Environmental Consequences. OECD. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/9789264307452-en>, doi:10.1787/9789264307452-en.

Sathre, R., Scown, C.D., Kavvada, O., Hendrickson, T.P., 2015. Energy and climate effects of second-life use of electric vehicle batteries in California through 2050. Journal of Power Sources 288, 82–91. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2015.04.097>, doi:10.1016/j.jpowsour.2015.04.097.

Sun, L., Dong, H., Dai, Y., Dong, J., Fujii, M., Geng, Y., Lou, Z., Liu, X., 2024. Environmental benefit of recycling plastics from waste electrical and electronic equipment. Resources, Conservation and Recycling 211, 107855. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2024.107855>, doi:10.1016/j.resconrec.2024.107855.

Sutkar, P.R., Gadewar, R.D., Dhulap, V.P., 2023. Recent trends in degradation of microplastics in the environment: A state-of-the-art review. Journal of Hazardous Materials Advances 11, 100343. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.hazadv.2023.100343>, doi:10.1016/j.hazadv.2023.100343.

Wu, W., Lin, B., Xie, C., Elliott, R.J., Radcliffe, J., 2020. Does energy storage provide a profitable second life for electric vehicle batteries? Energy Economics 92, 105010. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2020.105010>, doi:10.1016/j.eneco.2020.105010.

Highlights

Reusability analysis metrics for 2nd life electrical and mechanical battery components

Dimitra Spanoudaki, Vasileios Apostoloudas, Elisavet Elvanoglou

- Second-Life batteries
- Mechanical waste
- Electrical waste
- Reusability analysis
- Circularity

Preprint not peer reviewed

Reusability analysis metrics for 2nd life electrical and mechanical battery components^{*}

Dimitra Spanoudaki^{a,*}, Vasileios Apostoloudas^{a,1} and Elisavet Elvanoglou^a

^a*Sunlight Group Energy Systems, Lithium - Research and Development Department, , Xanthi, 67200, Greece*

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

2nd life batteries
reusability analysis
waste management
lithium-ion batteries

ABSTRACT

In the near future, the number of electric vehicle (EV) batteries, no longer appropriate for automotive use, will dramatically increase. At the end of their warranties the expected EV batteries nominal capacity will vary between 70–80%. This is also the First-Life End-Of-Life threshold adopted by most within the automotive industry. Whereas these EV batteries will not be appropriate for automotive applications, they could be repurposed for stationary energy storage systems as Second-Life batteries. The new Battery Regulation of the European Union is enforced as of July 2023 and ensures that batteries within the EU have a low carbon footprint due to the reduction of resources required, the reduction of raw materials (from non-EU countries) and an increase of reuse and recycling in Europe. The result of this act is the shift to a circular economy growth model, the increase in security of supply for raw materials and energy overall and the enhancement of the EU's strategic autonomy. Working towards the direction of the circular economy growth model, we present the first steps a battery industry must take for the repurposing of 1st life traction batteries (industrial EV's) for an industrial stationary energy storage system. More specifically, we address the issue of the reusability of first life electrical and mechanical components (except for the lithium-ion cells), and we introduce quantitative and decision-making tools for an automatic and safer choice of these components for the Second-Life applications. The methodology of the reusability analysis of a Second-Life battery, includes the evaluation of the Bill of Materials (BOM) list of the battery system, the grouping and sorting of the different materials, their evaluation from engineers and blue-collar workers and the final assessment with a decision matrix. The criteria introduced in the decision matrix include the price, the volume, the warranty, the environmental impact, the availability (in the market) and the recyclability of the electrical and mechanical components. The results of this assessment show a trend on how many of the electrical and mechanical components are suggested to be recycled or repurposed for Second-Life applications based on each one of the main criteria we introduced in the decision matrix.

Acronym	Meaning
EV	Electric Vehicle
BS	Battery System
BOM	Bill of Materials
NMC	Nickel manganese Cobalt cells
LFP	Lithium Iron Phosphate
BESS	Battery Energy Storage System

Table 1

Abbreviations related to battery systems and circular economy notions.

1. Introduction

Since the Industrial Revolution, the dominating economic growth model is a linear model that serves the purposes of a rapid and efficient production of goods, without regard to environmental resources. In the last few decades,

^{*}Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor CINEA can be held responsible for these issues. Grant Agreement number: 101137615

^{*}Corresponding author

 d.spanoudaki@sunlight.gr (D. Spanoudaki)

ORCID(s): 0000-0001-7511-2910 (D. Spanoudaki)

¹These authors contributed equally to this manuscript.

manufacturing firms have been facing great challenges including resource scarcity, soaring prices of energy and materials, environmental pollutions and societal pressures. These challenges have forced governments to regulate in favor of a new circular economy growth model and firms to find ways to adopt circular methodologies and thinking of production procedures Lacy, Long and Spindler (2020); OECD (2019).

A circular economy is a regenerative economic model in which resource input emissions, waste and energy leakage are minimized by slowing, narrowing and closing the material and energy loops Foundation (2015). A circular economy aims to keep resources in productive use for a possible, extract the maximum value from them whilst in use, then recover and regenerate products and/or raw materials at the end of their service life. By closing the loop of material flows throughout the product life cycle and using the raw material and energy through multiple phases, the circular approach seeks to ultimately decouple economic growth from constrained natural resources.

A robust example of an international try for efficient circular management is that of the Li-ion batteries. The exponential increase in the adoption of electric vehicles (EVs) poses a pressing concern about the end-of-life management of the Li-ion batteries. By 2030, it is expected that more than 145 million EVs will be in the society. Li-ion batteries have a lifespan ranging from 5 - 15 years and their capacity reduction drops as much as 20%. Due to their

Figure 1: Reusability analysis methodology for the evaluation of the components of a 1st life battery system.

decreased performance in EVs and due to concerns about their safety, new applications have been investigated for these batteries in the field of Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS), giving them a second life in another less demanding applications Sathre, Scown, Kavvada and Hendrickson (2015); Chirumalla, Kulkov, Vu and Rahic (2023); Dong, Liang, Li, Kim, Shen and Wallington (2023); Cusenza, Guarino, Longo, Ferraro and Cellura (2019); Neigum and Wang (2024); Wu, Lin, Xie, Elliott and Radcliffe (2020).

Despite the growing body of literature on reuse and repurposing of EV batteries, a discernible gap persists in the examination of the repurposing of the waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) that they co-exist with the to-be-repurposed battery cells inside a battery pack.

In this research, we aim to address the issue of the reusability of WEEE and to introduce quantitative and decision-making tools for an automatic and rational choice of WEEE to be reused. We consider the by-default repurposing of battery modules, for a second life BESS and we evaluate the reusability of WEEE Sun, Dong, Dai, Dong, Fujii, Geng, Lou and Liu (2024)

This manuscript consists of: 1) the introduction of the decision-making methodology, 2) the application of the methodology to traction batteries and 3) the discussion of the results.

2. Methodology

To evaluate the re-usability of the components of the 1st life battery system and the possibility of re-purposing it to a 2nd life BESS, we developed a methodology that includes the

assessment of the components through the Bill of Materials (BOM) of the 1st life battery system. Figure 1 presents the methodology and the basic steps identified are the following:

- The BOM list (Table 1) is the main tool to proceed in the reusability analysis. The BOM list is the main list that includes every mechanical, electronic or other (sticker, glues) component that is used to build a battery system (Fig. 2). It consists of various levels, from the higher systems to the lower subsystems. As we move from the higher to the lower level, we move from the outer part of the battery to the inner part and from the bigger parts to smaller ones. As a first step, we extract the important BOM levels for this assessment. For the 2nd life BESS, the modules of the 1st life battery system are going to be reused, so we will take into consideration the higher levels. In the example of the Table 2, we are going to evaluate the components of the levels 1, 2, and 3 because they are higher systems to the module (level 4), and we are not going to evaluate the re-usability of the levels 5 and 6, because they exist in the module that is going to be re-used.
- The 2nd step is the 01 Assessment (Fig. 1). This assessment is done by 3 reviewers – an electrical engineer, a mechanical engineer and a blue-collar worker – who decide if a battery component is going to be disposed or reused based on their experience and their knowledge. If they choose its disposal, they grade the battery component with 0 and if they choose its reuse,

Level	Component Description	Quantity	Units
1	battery display	1	pieces
1	CAN BUS cable	7	meters
1	plastic head bolt	10	pieces
1	rubber sheet vibration	1	
1	cable tie	30	pieces
2	NMC modules 85 kWh	16	pieces
2	contactor SGX 150 A	4	pieces
2	fuse GigaFuse 100 V - 400 A	1	pieces
2	cable tie	80	pieces
2	silicone tube	6	meters
2	washers M4 INOX A2	24	pieces
2	NMC module	4	pieces
3	slave board	4	pieces
3	master board	1	pieces
3	screws	126	pieces
3	thermistors	2	pieces
3	washers M4 INOX A2	68	pieces
4	Pre-assembled module NMC	1	pieces
4	NMC cell	76	pieces
4	bolt M6x12 HEX DIN 933 INOX A4	224	pieces
4	Sticker "Minus - "	4	pieces
5	cable UL	6	meters
5	silicone tube	7	meters
5	thermistor	32	pieces
5	Minifit female connector	6	pieces
6	glue	100	milli-liters
6	thermal pipe	1	meters
6	wire yellow	1	meters
6	wire blue	1	meters

Table 2
An example of a Bill of Materials list of a battery system.

they grade the battery component with 1. In case of doubts, our recommendation to the reviewers is to choose 1. After their evaluation, the decision is made from the final score produced by summarizing the 0's and 1's. Scoring above 2 means that a component can be reused and below that, it needs to be disposed, having no further usage for 2nd life battery system or any other kind of re-purposing process. If 2 of the 3 reviewers have chosen that a component A is going to be disposed (0) then their opinion prevails against the one reviewer. The goal for the 01 Assessment is an initial evaluation of reuse of the module components on quantitative level.

- The 3rd step is the re-evaluation of the positive 01 Assessment results based on well-defined decision criteria inserted on a Pugh decision matrix Burge (2006). If there is a value in the battery components that can be generated for a 2nd life application, the decision criteria will show it clearly.

In the next sections, a rigorous analysis of the steps is given.

Figure 2: Some of the components of a battery system Bill of Materials.

Groups	Parts	Material
1	washers	metal
2	screws	metal
3	bolts	metal
4	cables	plastic, metal
5	silicone, plastic, heat tubing	plastic
6	nuts	metal
7	harness	plastic, metal
8	bus bars	metal

Table 3

Grouping of the various components of a battery system under a common name.

3. Methodology

3.1. Bill of Materials and 01 Assessment

A BOM list is a file that consists of the battery levels, the component description, their quantities and their units (Table 2). The levels refer to the level of the BS, meaning that the smaller numbers, i.e. 1, refer to the higher and outer level of the BS and as we move towards the smaller numbers, we move to the inner parts of a BS and to smaller components.

The component description is created by the designer of the 1st life BS based on a standard trend that developed and adopted by the industries. It contains information about the sizes of mechanical parts (i.e. Washers M4 INOX A2), current and voltage limits of electrical parts (i.e. Contactor SGX 150A, colors of wires (i.e. Wire yellow) etc. In the methodology, we grouped various components into eight categories (Table 3) based on their functionality, that is: 1) washers, 2) screws, 3) bolts, 4) cables, 5) silicone, plastic, heat tubing, 6) nus, 7) harness, 8) bus bars, so as to simplify their evaluation and not taking into account their sizes, colors or other characteristics that are irrelevant to the reusability decisions. Also, we indicate the material they are made of, that is metal, plastic or both of them.

3.2. Decision Matrix

Fundamentally a Pugh matrix can be used whenever there is a need to decide amongst several alternatives. Although specifically developed by Stuart Pugh to help in selecting between a few design alternatives, the tools have in recent years be used in general-purpose decision-making aid because its ease of use. The sole purpose of a Pugh decision matrix is to handle the inconsistent and irrational decisions of human beings. Because, the 01 Assessment of this research is highly based on personal choices of the evaluators, we need a more robust way to avoid biased decisions that we will present a distorted image of which component is being repurposed and which one is going to be recycled. For that requirement of objectiveness to be achieved, general criteria are selected, to research their impact on the remaining components after the 01 Assessment. These criteria are defined on Table 4 and in the list below:

- **Price:** This criterion represents the value of the component in the market. Higher prices mean components

with higher values and thus their repurposing process should be considered very wisely before any decision for recycling them.

- **Volume:** Volume of a component is highly considered during product development, due to product's final size and waste management. Waste management is an everyday issue for industries and gets of higher importance when its volume rises. To resolve this, in the spectrum of 2nd life BESS, components with large volume need to be reconsidered for reuse/repurpose than recycling, and this criterion showcases that. If a component has a volume above a specific range is accepted for reuse/repurpose, and below that range goes for recycling. This criterion is intended to set a limit to the quantitative evaluation, because many components to be reused, may have low volume (cables, screws, nuts, bolts).
- **Warranty:** The warranty of a component is an extremely important criterion because it is strongly linked to the safety of the product. A component, that its warranty has expired, will be treated differently than any other component, as the quality control will be more extensive and stricter. In general, the state of warranty of a BS is one of the most important reusability indicators because it has an indirect reference to the safety of the BS components.
- **Environmental Impact:** Some of the battery components have higher environmental impact if they are disposed accidentally or not to the environment and if they are sent to recycling. For example, bolts and nuts are consisting only of metal and their environmental impact its low, because they degrade by atmospheric oxidation if they are disposed in the environment. A wire that consists of metal and plastic it has higher environmental impact because the plastics do not decompose naturally in the environment, but they degrade to microplastics, that affect extremely the ecosystem in the long-term period (Sutkar, Gade-war and Dhulap (2023)). At last, a component with high environmental impact, i.e. electrochemical cell (battery cell), except of metal and plastic has toxic chemicals that in case of their leakage, affect the environment in the short term.
- **Availability:** The criterion of the availability of components is linked with their availability in the market and possible distortion of the availability due to geopolitical changes, supply chain disruptions, biological dangers. For example, during the COVID-19 pandemic, the semiconductor industry was severely hit, thus disrupting the industry of PCBs, a vital component for the batteries, and every electronic device nowadays. The availability of a component in the market and the constant tracking of this criterion can help the businesses earn a significant strategic advantage

Criteria Definition	Price	Volume	Warranty	Environm. impact	Availability	Recyclability
Reuse +	100 € / unit	100 cm ³	10 years	High	Low	Low
Repurpose B	10 - 100 € / unit	10 – 100 cm ³	1 – 10 years	Medium	Medium	Medium
Recycle -	10 € / unit	10 cm ³	1 year or no warranty	Low	High	High

Table 4
Decision criteria definitions based on the Reuse, Repurpose, and Recycle goals.

	Component A	Component B	Component C	Component D
Criterion 1	B	-	+	B
Criterion 2	B	-	+	B
Criterion 3	B	+	+	-
Criterion 4	B	-	+	-
Criterion 5	B	B	+	-
Criterion 6	B	B	B	+
Criterion 7	B	+	B	B
Criterion 8	B	-	-	-
Criterion 9	B	+	-	B
Criterion 10	B	+	+	-
Total +	0	4	6	1
Total -	0	-4	-2	-5
Total score	0	0	4	-4

Table 5
Example of a Pugh decision matrix.

and estimate if there is a need to reuse a component and regulate disruptions in the supply chain.

- **Recyclability:** Strongly linked to the criterion of the environmental impact of the components, as a component that has a lower environmental impact, has a higher recyclability. For example, a metal that has a lower environmental impact it's easy to recycle by melting it. By increasing the complexity and the chemical basis of the components, the recyclability complexity increases as well. This criterion also includes the cost of recycling as well. Considering that, in our example of a metal, it still has a higher recyclability because it will cost less to recycle it.

Table 5 shows a completed Pugh Matrix for four hypothetical components called A, B, C and D, which can be found along the top of the matrix. The components were evaluated against 10 hypothetical criteria. In constructing a Pugh matrix, on component, in this example "Component A" is selected as the "baseline". The baseline scores as "B" against all the criteria. The other components are then compared in a pairwise fashion against component A for each of the criteria. If a component is:

- Better than the baseline, a "+" is entered in the appropriate cell.
- Worse than the baseline, a "-" is entered in the appropriate cell.
- The same as the baseline, a "B" is entered in the appropriate cell.

For the hypothetical components and criteria of the Table 5:

- Component A is the baseline for all criteria.
- Component B is worse than component A in the criteria 1, 2, 4, 8.
- Component C is worse than component A in the criteria 8, 9.
- Component D is worse than component A in the criteria 3, 4, 5, 8 and 10.

The overall decision is presented in the total score, where "B" = 0, "+" = +1 and "-" = -1, and:

- If the score is 0, then the component is in the baseline and goes for re-purposing/ reusing.
- If the score is positive, then the component will be reused or repurposed.
- If the score is negative, the component will be recycled.

In this research, we do not aim to distinguish between the notions re-purposing and re-using, but we consider that the value of the component is regenerated and is going to be used again in a 2nd life application.

4. Results and Discussion

Three reviewers, an electrical engineer, a mechanical engineer and a blue-collar worker, filled the 01 Assessment

	Contactor	Bolts	Module 1P16S	Battery Control Unit	Battery Socket	Flat Cable	Washer
Price	B	-	+	+	-	-	-
Volume	B	+	+	+	-	-	+
Environmental Impact	B	-	+	+	-	B	-
Availability	B	-	+	+	B	B	-
Recyclability	B	-	+	B	B	B	-
Total Score	0	-4	5	4	-3	-2	-4
Result	Pass	Fail	Pass	Pass	Fail	Fail	Fail

Table 6
Pugh Decision matrix examples from the BS.

Figure 3: 01 Assessment for the traction battery.

matrix and chose if the components of a first life battery system (a traction battery) can be reused or disposed

With the Pugh decision matrix and the 6 criteria – price, volume, warranty, environmental impact, availability, recyclability – we further assess the results from the 01 Assessment (4). The 38.5 % of the battery components can be re-purposed in a 2nd life BS or reused in a 1st life BS, and the 61.5 % can be recycled.

Further analysis of the 38.5 % of the reused components shows that the 25.6 % are electrical components, the 7.7 % are mechanical components and the 5.1 % are other components (mostly plastics).

The low percentage of the mechanical components is due to the nuts, bolts, washers and other mechanical components that must be inspected for corrosion signs or other defects before being reused in another application. Other mechanical components might also need to be redesigned to fit the 2nd life BS. This is dependent from the application, its complexity and the components that need to be added during manufacturing.

Figure 4: Reusability analysis results after the Pugh Analysis Assessment

Table 6 shows the results of some important battery components. The main conclusions from the Table 6 are the following:

- **Bolts:** Score -4. Passed from the one criterion; decreased in total for 2nd life BS.
- **Module 1P16S:** Score 6. Passed from all the criteria for 2nd life BS.
- **Battery Control Unit:** Score 4. Passed from all the criteria for 2nd life BS.
- **Battery Socket:** Score -3. Passed from half of the criteria but declined for 2nd life.
- **Flat cable:** Score -2. Passed from four criteria but neglected for the remaining two and got declined for 2nd life.
- **Washer:** Score -4. Passed only from one criterion, neglected from the rest and declined for 2nd life.

The above examples show that a component can be neglected for 2nd life purposes, while being accepted at least by one criterion. A question that arises from this observation is the following: “Which components, accepted for 2nd life purposes, passed the criterion X?”

In Figure 5, two bars are shown for each criterion. The first bar indicates the percentage of the components that

Figure 5: A) Reuse/ Repurpose results of the Pugh analysis matrix, i) one-by-one criterion, ii) compared to total results..

accepted a positive sign (+) in the Pugh analysis matrix and the second bar of each criterion shows the normalized percentage from the total BOM list results. The last bar (BOM results) includes the percentage of accepted components from the Pugh analysis. For the criteria Volume, Warranty, Environmental impact and Recyclability, we observe that the decrease is high, which means that many components got neglected for 2nd life, while initially passed those criteria (one-by-one).

Figure 5 shows at least that a lot of components get declined from finding application on 2nd life BS. To better understand the connection of each criterion on the result, by normalizing the percentage values of reuse/ repurpose is normalized (Figure 6a) and two trending lines occur:

1. The Price and the Availability criteria, having initially (by one-by-one evaluation) 100 % regarding the Reuse/Repurpose result, affect the most the Pugh analysis. Between these two, Price criterion has more impact on the result, while having the minimum percentage decrease.
2. The Volume criterion is either the most neutral or the most controlling factor in the Pugh analysis. By neutral, it means that it does not having much impact on the result, which is due to the many components that passed this criterion. In addition, every component that got accepted from the Pugh analysis, seems to have passed the Volume criterion. This means that a component possibly needs to have this criterion passed to be accepted for Reuse/Repurpose. As initially planned, adding this criterion was a try to control the quantitative parameter.

Figure 6b shows the normalized results with the total studied BOM list , where the percentages for the components to be Reused/Repurposed or Recycled are 6 % less than the Pugh analysis ones. Figure 6c presents the Reuse/Repurpose and Recycle quantitative results for all the reusability analysis for 2nd life BS, in a nested pie chart format. In the center, the 01 Assessment results are shown. On the next level, the Pugh analysis results are shown, combined with the total studied BOM list (having again the Disposal percentage).

On the third and last level, the breakdown of the previous percentages, by component type (Mechanical, Electrical, Other) is shown. After the assessment of the Pugh analysis, the results show that the 32.6 % are going to be reused for 2nd life BS, the 52.2 % of the components are going to be recycled and the remaining 15.2 % will be disposed of. In summary, regarding components to be reused and repurposed, mechanical components show a huge loss, where the majority is selected to be recycled, as they are customized components designed only for 1st life BS. The quantities of electrical components are the most of the components that are to be reused, and the same amount is also forwarded to be recycled. To manage the high recycling result (52.2 %) on the next level of analysis, during disassembly, a thorough quality control is required for these components.

5. Conclusions and Perspectives

The key criteria that influence the reusability of the WEEE components of a traction battery are the price and the availability. With Price having a slightly higher impact. Volume acts as a prerequisite criterion for component acceptance. The 32.6 % of components are viable for Reuse/Repurpose, mostly electrical components. The 52.2 % are directed to Recycling, primarily Mechanical components due to their first-life-specific designs. The 15.2 % are marked for disposal. The current analysis suggests a need for targeted disassembly procedures, especially for components marked for Recycling. Implementing stringent quality checks can enhance the yield of reusable or repurposable components.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Dimitra Spanoudaki: Conceptualization of this study, Methodology, Writing - Original draft preparation, Review - editing, Investigation, Supervision, Project Administration.
Vasileios Apostoloudas: Conceptualization of this study, Methodology, Writing - Original draft preparation, Review - editing, Investigation, Visualization.
Elisavet Elvanoglou: Data curation, Review.

References

- Burge, S., 2006. The Systems Engineering Tool Box. Burge Hughes Walsh. URL: <https://www.burgehugheswalsh.co.uk/Uploaded/1/Documents/FMA-Tool-v1-1.pdf>.
- Chirumalla, K., Kulkov, I., Vu, F., Rahic, M., 2023. Second life use of li-ion batteries in the heavy-duty vehicle industry: Feasibilities of remanufacturing, repurposing, and reusing approaches. *Sustainable Production and Consumption* 42, 351–366. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2023.10.007>, doi:10.1016/j.spc.2023.10.007.
- Cusenza, M.A., Guarino, F., Longo, S., Ferraro, M., Cellura, M., 2019. Energy and environmental benefits of circular economy strategies: The case study of reusing used batteries from electric vehicles. *Journal of Energy Storage* 25, 100845. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2019.100845>, doi:10.1016/j.est.2019.100845.
- Dong, Q., Liang, S., Li, J., Kim, H.C., Shen, W., Wallington, T.J., 2023. Cost, energy, and carbon footprint benefits of second-life electric vehicle battery use. *iScience* 26, 107195. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2023.107195>, doi:10.1016/j.isci.2023.107195.

Figure 6: a. Pugh analysis normalized results, b. Pugh matrix results correlated on total quantities from the BOM list, c) Reusability analysis results for the 2nd life BS.

Foundation, E.M., 2015. Growth within: A circular economy vision for a competitive Europe. Ellen MacArthur Foundation. URL: <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/growth-within-a-circular-economy-vision-for-a-competitive-europe>.

Lacy, P., Long, J., Spindler, W., 2020. The Circular Economy Handbook: Realizing the Circular Advantage. Palgrave Macmillan UK. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1057/978-1-349-95968-6>, doi:10.1057/978-1-349-95968-6.

Neigum, K., Wang, Z., 2024. Technology, economic, and environmental analysis of second-life batteries as stationary energy storage: A review. Journal of Energy Storage 103, 114393. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2024.114393>, doi:10.1016/j.est.2024.114393.

OECD, 2019. Global Material Resources Outlook to 2060: Economic Drivers and Environmental Consequences. OECD. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/9789264307452-en>, doi:10.1787/9789264307452-en.

Sathre, R., Scown, C.D., Kavvada, O., Hendrickson, T.P., 2015. Energy and climate effects of second-life use of electric vehicle batteries in California through 2050. Journal of Power Sources 288, 82–91. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2015.04.097>, doi:10.1016/j.jpowsour.2015.04.097.

Sun, L., Dong, H., Dai, Y., Dong, J., Fujii, M., Geng, Y., Lou, Z., Liu, X., 2024. Environmental benefit of recycling plastics from waste electrical and electronic equipment. Resources, Conservation and Recycling 211, 107855. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2024.107855>, doi:10.1016/j.resconrec.2024.107855.

Sutkar, P.R., Gadewar, R.D., Dhulap, V.P., 2023. Recent trends in degradation of microplastics in the environment: A state-of-the-art review. Journal of Hazardous Materials Advances 11, 100343. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.hazadv.2023.100343>, doi:10.1016/j.hazadv.2023.100343.

Wu, W., Lin, B., Xie, C., Elliott, R.J., Radcliffe, J., 2020. Does energy storage provide a profitable second life for electric vehicle batteries? Energy Economics 92, 105010. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2020.105010>, doi:10.1016/j.eneco.2020.105010.